

MAPPING PITCH CLASSES AND SOUND OBJECTS: A BRIDGE BETWEEN KLUMPENHOUWER NET- WORKS AND SCHAEFFER'S TARTYP

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ABSTRACT

We present an interactive generative method for bridging between sound-object composition rooted in Pierre Schaeffer's TARTYP taxonomy and transformational pitch-class composition ingrained in Klumpenhouwer Networks. We create a quantitative representation of sound objects within an ordered sound space. We use this representation to define a probability-based mapping of pitch classes to sound objects. We demonstrate the implementation of the method in a real-time compositional process that also utilizes our previous work on a TARTYP generative grammar tool and an interactive K-Network tool.

1. INTRODUCTION

For hundreds of years, musical analysis focused almost exclusively on pitch in the description of musical structures and compositional unity. The appearance of electronic music in the twentieth century shook these foundations, revealing a palette of non-pitch sounds or not-entirely-pitch sounds that can play a role in music composition. Following the creative work within this expanded world of sounds came attempts to formalize its theoretical understanding, most notably by Pierre Schaeffer and his idea of *musique concrète* (concrete music). Contemporary composers, in particular of compositions for live performers and electronics, commonly use pitch-based composition alongside sound-based composition. However, few attempts were made to connect these two approaches in one unifying musical framework.

This study has evolved from previous studies in which we introduced two generative compositional tools: the TARTYP generative grammar tool [1,2] and the interactive K-Network tool [2]. The former is for use within the domain of sound objects and is based on Pierre Schaeffer's TARTYP taxonomy. The latter is for use within the domain of pitch classes and is based on David Lewin's transformation theory and Henry Klumpenhouwer's networks. Both tools support real-time composition and computer improvisation. Both tools share similar mechanics and computational principles, as they are both based on traversing through search trees. This similarity put forward the idea of finding a method to bridge between the two domains of pitch classes and sound objects, to produce a single musical structure and a unified

compositional process. While we approach this task from a generative compositional perspective, we are nevertheless aiming to find a meaningful method consistent with the analytical context from which it evolves, i.e., transformational theory and the TARTYP.

Transformational theory, a prominent method for analyzing pitch structures in twentieth-century music, is derived from musical set theory, in which the collection of 12 pitch classes is considered to be the pitch space of music. Klumpenhouwer Networks, a major component of transformational theory, reside within this ordered space of 12 pitch classes. The space of electronic music and concrete music in particular is much less defined. Nevertheless, one may look at Schaeffer's TARTYP and identify in this taxonomy the potential for defining several sound spaces based on the table's division into sub-collections of sound objects [1,2]. Klumpenhouwer Networks' isographic principles are facilitated by the quantitatively comparable characteristics of the ordered elements of the space, i.e., the pitch classes. These characteristics, however, do not easily translate to the textually defined sound objects of the TARTYP.

In this paper, we first present a method for organizing sound objects, i.e., concrete sound samples, in ordered spaces based on quantitative analysis of the sounds' spectral characteristics. Following the definition of such ordered sound spaces we present a mapping between pitch classes and sound objects. This mapping uses additional aspects of quantitative spectral analysis of sounds to determine probability-based relationships between the fixed pitch-class space and arbitrary collections of sound objects. Since the latter may refer to any size collection of sounds, our mapping is not 1-to-1 but rather 1-to-many or many-to-many, depending on the size of the collection. With this mapping, we can use the pitch-class based interactive K-Network tool to generate musical structures of sound objects as well as the TARTYP generative grammar tool to generate musical structures of pitch classes.

2. BACKGROUND

In [3], David Lewin formally introduces the Generalized Interval Systems (GIS). A GIS is defined by the tuple $(S, IVLS, int)$ in which S is a space of elements, $IVLS$ is a group of intervals and int is a function mapping S to $IVLS$ [3]. In chapters two through four of [3] Lewin provides multiple examples of GISs describing a variety of musi-

cal elements and musical material in the pitch, time and timbre domains. In all of these GISs, the elements in the spaces S are obtained by a quantifiable process or an underlying formula that makes them compatible with a mapping to measured intervals. For example, the chromatic scale space is obtained by integer addition and its reduction to 12-pitch-class space is obtained by integral multiple of 12 [3]. A similar example is the Just intonation GIS of which S is a space all pitches generated by Just intonation from a given pitch and $IVLS$ is a “group under multiplication of all rational numbers that can be written in the form $2^a3^b5^c$, where a , b , and c are integers [3].”

Lewin’s approach to timbre analysis is similar. His first example of timbral GIS describes classes of harmonic steady-state sounds [3]. A class of harmonic steady-state sounds includes all the harmonic sounds of which the first, third and fifth partial have the same power, described by the tuple $s=(s(1),s(3),s(5))$. $IVLS$ and interval transformations in this GIS are defined by proportional amplification or attenuation of the power of each partial. More specifically, the interval transformation tuple $i=(i(1),i(3),i(5))$ when applied to s will produce a sound in which the power of the first partial is i times $s(1)$, the power of the third partial is i times $s(3)$ and the power of the fifth partial is i times $s(5)$. Lewin regard this GIS as commutative, i.e., all sound classes in this space are related under the $int(s,t) = i$ function. In other words, any sound in class s can be transformed to a sound in class t by multiplying its first, third and fifth partial by i . In practical terms, Lewin’s choice of elements, i.e., the steady state of sounds and three harmonic partials, are limited in their ability to describe differences in timbre. Together with the restriction of proportional power relations the sound classes in Lewin’s timbral GIS are all of similar timbre.

In his second example, Lewin expand the sound class definition to include eight partials of harmonic sound, $s=(s(1),\dots,s(8))$ [3]. He then combines the timbral GIS with a time-point GIS to create a direct-product GIS that describes the change of power (amplitude) over time in regard to each partial. He calls this developing spectrum GIS (DVSP). According to Lewin, the DVSP is comparable with the way Moorer and Grey described the frequency spectrum of sounds in [4]. In fact, the DVSP is an abstract representation of the process described by Moorer and Grey. It does not provide a practical way to differentiate between concrete sounds, i.e., sound objects. Such a comparison is essential for the definition of a sound space in the same way that distinguishing between pitch classes is essential for the definition of a pitch-class space.

In contrast, Schaeffer’s TARTYP taxonomy is founded on comparison between sound objects based on their characteristics in the time and spectral domains. Schaeffer uses the terms *fixed mass*, *definite pitch*, *complex pitch*, *not very variable mass* and *unpredictable variation of mass* to describe sound objects in the spectral domain. He uses the terms *impulse*, *formed iteration*, *(iterative) nonexistent facture*, *(iterative) unpredictable facture*, *formed sustain*, *(held) nonexistent facture*, and *(held) unpredictable facture* to describe sound objects in

the time domain [1,2]. Moreover, Schaeffer divides the table into sub-collections of sound-objects, some of which are notated in the table while others are clearly discussed in Schaefferian studies [5]. Sound objects in a sub-collection may be similar in some characteristics but differ in other characteristics. For example, the sound objects marked N’ X’ and Y’ in the *Balanced* sub-collections all have the same time domain characteristic, i.e., *impulse* (or a very short duration). However they differ in their frequency domain characteristic: N’ is *definite pitch*; X’ is *complex pitch*; and Y’ is *not very variable mass*. While the meaning of Schaeffer’s terminology is the subject of some debate by scholars, the TARTYP taxonomy is a prominent theory of electronic music and is constantly being explored for analytical and practical uses [6].

The differences between Schaeffer’s approach and Lewin’s approach are striking. Schaeffer’s terminology is all descriptive, subjective and incompatible with any underlying quantitative formula. Schaeffer provides an alphanumeric notation that represents sound object classes [1,2], however, this is not a quantitative representation suited for mathematical definitions. On the other hand, Schaeffer considers a wide variety of possible timbres, while Lewin’s two timbral GISs deal only with harmonic sounds. As such they describe only one category out of the four categories of timbre defined by Schaeffer in the spectral domain of the TARTYP, the category of *definite pitch*. In the time domain Schaeffer uses descriptive definitions of duration with no measuring scale. In particular, Schaeffer uses the term *undefined* to describe very long sounds. Lewin’s temporal and rhythmic GISs are all based on measurable time units such as beats and seconds/milliseconds.

Brain Kane [7] describes the difference between Schaeffer’s concrete music and pitch-based music (abstract music) with the following words:

Abstract music, which Schaeffer contrasted with *musicque concrète*, was music that began with the note, organized its musical thinking in terms of the note, and then draped it in the guise of acoustic or electronic sound.

Kane continues:

Concrete music was to be the exact opposite—a music that began with sounds recorded from the world and sought to perceive in them (and abstract from them) musical values.

In [7], Kane describes Schaeffer’s early concrete music compositional attempts and the search for a basic theoretical unit:

Throughout his experiments, Schaeffer remains in the grip of two recurrent desires: a compositional desire to construct music from concrete objects—no matter how unsatisfactory the initial results—and a theoretical desire to find a vocabulary, solfège, or method upon which to ground such music. In those early days, Schaeffer’s improvised compositional techniques were indissociable from an improvised ontology, not only in search of a concrete music but a basic theoretical unit upon which to compose such music.

While being subjected to multiple redefinitions, this basic theoretical unit almost from the very beginning of concrete music was the sound object [5,7]. Schaeffer's writings and consequent Schaefferian studies, in particular Michel Chion's *Guide to Sound Objects* [5], offer almost exclusively verbal definitions and descriptions of the meaning of the term sound object. As mentioned before, Schaefferian theory does not offer a quantitative representation of sound objects that is comparable with the set theory representation of pitch classes as integers mod-12. The main reason for this is probably Schaeffer's focus on the perception of sound in its complexity, i.e., both in the frequency and time domains, as demonstrated by the TARTYP. However, it is also possible that if Schaeffer had available some of the acoustic analysis and machine learning tools available today, he would have attempted to quantify this basic unit of his theory. Here, we do not attempt to quantify the sound object. Instead we will attempt to use modern acoustic analysis tools to create a bridge between Schaeffer's descriptive perspective and Lewin's more quantitative view.

3. PITCH-CLASS SPACES AND SOUND SPACES

In spite of its descriptive and ambiguous nature, in previous studies we were able to apply a generative-grammar-based computational process to the TARTYP taxonomy and to incorporate it in a generative compositional tool [1,2]. We applied a very similar process to Klumpenhauer Networks in order to translate this analytical method to a generative compositional tool [2]. To create a bridge between the Schaefferian and the Lewinian approaches within a computational environment, we attempt to define a quantitative representation of sound objects (i.e., concrete sound samples) that will function similarly to the use of integers mod-12 in the representation of the 12 pitch classes.

Pitch classes are based on the principle of octave equivalency where an integer represents the class of all pitches with the same note name, i.e. pitches that are one or more octaves apart. For example, 0 represents the class of all pitches with the note name C. At the same time, the set of integers mod-12 defines the location of pitch classes within an ordered space and provides the arguments for various transformation formulas. The space of pitch classes is ordered in the same ascending order as the octave on the piano, (0, 1, ..., 10, 11 and C, C#, ..., A#, B). However, a motion from a pitch class represented by lower value integer to a pitch class represented by higher integer, due to octave equivalency, does not always mean a motion from low sounding pitch to higher sounding pitch. In Figure 1, the two notes are respectively members of pitch class 0 and pitch class 3. The transformation here is upwards transposition T_3 . However, in the musical surface it is a downward leap of nine semitones.

Transformations such as transposition and inversion create equivalence relationships between pitch classes. As shown in Figure 1 pitch class 0 is transformed into pitch class 3 by T_3 transposition. While the space of pitch

classes is ordered by increasing integer values, due to these equivalence relationships none of the pitch classes receives greater importance or weight than the others. These characteristics of the pitch-class space are rooted in the atonal musical approach that avoids recognition of any tonal center. Therefore we may deduce that in the space of pitch classes, each pitch class occupies exactly the same portion of the space as the other pitch classes.

Figure 1. T_3 transposition composed out as downward leap of 9 semitones (a major 6th).

This would not necessarily be the case with sound spaces. Sound objects do not naturally fall into order. As we will see in the next section, we can use acoustic measurements to define a quantitative representation of sound samples and create an ordered space of sound objects. However, the principles of octave equivalency and equivalence relationships based on transposition and inversion cannot be effectively applied to sound objects. As previously demonstrated, the sub-collections of the TARTYP, which we identified as potential sound spaces, intentionally combine sound objects of diverse characteristics. In fact, as noted in [1,2] because of the structure of the table, each sound object in the TARTYP is characterized by a unique pair of attributes. Hence, to apply a process or a transformation that will achieve some sort of equivalence relations between these sound objects seems to miss the point of this taxonomy.

To generalize we acknowledge that sound objects are not equivalent under transformations such transposition and inversion. We also acknowledge that sound objects within a sound space may not have equal weight and therefore do not necessarily occupy the same portion of the sound space. In the next section, along with the creation of ordered spaces of sound objects, we will use acoustic measurements to define the portion each sound occupies within the space, i.e., the sound space internal segmentation.

4. METHOD

To create a mapping between the fixed space of pitch classes and any arbitrary collection of sounds we use a three-step method: in the first step we define an order within a collection of sounds; in the second step we define the portion of the space occupied by each sound, (which also can be described as the sound space's internal segmentation); and in the final step we map this sound space to the fixed and equally divided pitch-class space. In the following paragraphs we demonstrate the method by applying it to the sound recordings created by Schaeffer to exemplify the TARTYP [8]. These sound

examples are organized into sound spaces based on the division of the TARTYP to sub-collections [1,2].

4.1 Step 1: Sound Space Ordering

In step 1 we use the Pd patch in Figure 2 to create an order within a collection of sounds. This patch is based on a method described in [9]. It combines a bonk~ Pd object and the mfcc~ feature from the timbreID library [9,10]. The former is used to detect the sound's initial attack and to activate the mfcc~ feature, that in turn extracts the Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) of the sound's attack portion. We use a window size of 1024 samples and the mfcc~ object spacing value of 100 mel between filters in the filterbank. Hence we receive a vector of 38 coefficients from which we calculate the geometric mean.

Figure 2. A Pd patch defining an order within a space of sound objects.

Using an external Python script (within the pyext scripting object [11]) the Pd patch in Figure 2 first reads the content of a directory and saves the pathname of each sound file in the directory to a coll object. It then plays each file, detects the first attack in the file using the bonk~ object and extracts one vector of Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients from a 1024-sample window using the mfcc~ object (the sub-patch in Figure 3). This vector is stored in a tabletool object that is also used to calculate the geometric mean of the vector. This value is normalized ($\times 10^7$) and converted to an integer using the int object (the sub-patch in Figure 4). Consequently this integer is entered as an index number, along with the pathname of the sound file from which it was extracted, to another coll object. The latter is sorted in ascending order. The pathnames are output in this sorted order to a third coll object in which they receive a simple index number 0 to

n-1. This information is saved into an external text file that is used as input to step 2 of the method.

Figure 3. A sub-patch extracting an MFCC vector from a 1024-sample window using the mfcc~ object.

Figure 4. A sub-patch using the tabletool object to calculate the geometric mean of an MFCC vector.

Tables 1 through 4 show the orders that were defined by this patch for collections of sound files from Schaeffer's TARTYP examples as posted on [8]. The sound files of these examples received as their file name the alphanumeric notation of the sound object they represent as it appears in the TARTYP. The tables show the ordering of four sound spaces derived from the TARTYP sub-collections and their correlating generative grammars that were introduced in [1,2]. In particular sound space 1 includes the *Balanced* objects; sound space 2 includes the *Redundant and Homogeneous* objects both *Held* and *Iterative*; sound space 3 includes the *Accumulation* and *Sample* objects; and sound space 4 includes the rest of the *Excentric* objects, i.e., the bottom row of the TARTYP (see [2]). This division to sound spaces correlates with the incorporation of the TARTYP sub-collections and grammars in the interactive performance system SIG~ (see [6]). Each table shows the order that was defined for this sound space, the mean values and the normalized mean values converted to integers.

Index	Filename	Mean	Normalized
0	N.aif	0.0291414	291414
1	X'.aif	0.0361886	361885
2	Y'.aif	0.0480723	480723
3	X.aif	0.0511551	511551
4	N".aif	0.0559074	559074
5	Y.aif	0.0564293	564292
6	X".aif	0.0565979	565979
7	N'.aif	0.0616554	616554
8	Y".aif	0.0687108	687107

Table 1. Ordered sound space 1 of *Balanced* sound objects.

Index	Filename	Mean	Normalized
0	Hx.aif	0.0319039	319039
1	Zy.aif	0.0252379	252379
2	Hn.aif	0.104484	1044840
3	Zn.aif	0.108304	1083040
4	Zx.aif	0.131928	1319280
5	Tx.aif	0.178382	1783820
6	Tn.aif	0.233831	2338310

Table 2. Ordered sound space 2 of *Redundant and Homogeneous* sound objects both *Held* and *Iterative*.

Index	Filename	Mean	Normalized
0	Ey.aif	0.0282918	282917
1	Ex.aif	0.0363606	363606
2	An.aif	0.037019	370189
3	Ax.aif	0.0448542	448541
4	Ay.aif	0.0589824	589824
5	En.aif	0.106148	1061480
6	E.aif	0.145	1450000

Table 3. Ordered sound space 3 of *Accumulation* and *Sample* sound objects.

Index	Filename	Mean	Normalized
0	T.aiff	0.0189462	189461
1	W.aiff	0.029182	291819
2	A.aiff	0.0318919	318918
3	K.aiff	0.0444283	444283
4	P.aiff	0.0858835	858834
5	E.aiff	0.0917444	917443
6	Phi.aiff	0.117648	1176480

Table 4. Ordered sound space 4 of *Excentric* sound objects.

Our focus on the attack portion of the sound is based on studies showing the importance of the attack in defining timbral qualities of the sound [4,12]. The mfcc~ feature provide us with a compressed representation of a spectral domain energy distribution unique to the attack of each sound. By calculating the geometric mean of this list of coefficients, we can come up with a quantitative identifier unique to each sound that serves as the basis for ordering the sounds in the sound space.

4.2 Step 2: Sound Space Segmentation

As discussed in the previous section, sound objects are not equivalent under transformations. A sound space may include sound objects of different weight and have unequal internal segmentation. To represent the portion of the space occupied by each sound we analyze the sound's frequency spectrum throughout its entire duration. Our goal is to come up with one value that represents the sound's frequency domain energy level, i.e., the sound's weight within the space.

Similar to the patch in Figure 2, the patch in Figure 5 includes the mfcc~ feature from the timbreID library. In this step, however, we extract multiple MFCC vectors throughout the sound's entire duration and not just from the attack portion. Using again a window size of 1024 samples and the mfcc~ object spacing value of 100 mel between filters in the filterbank, the patch extracts an MFCC vector every 10 milliseconds. This time instead of calculating the geometric mean, we use Simpson's rule to approximate the area under the curve created by the MFCC vector. More specifically, the patch uses a Python module that incorporates the Python function "trapz". This area is a compressed representation of the accumulated energy in all the frequency bands of the sound at a specific time point. The number of vectors extracted from each sound varies based on the overall duration of the sound.

Figure 5. A Pd patch defining internal segmentations of sound spaces and pitch class to sound object probability mapping.

Since the MFCC vectors are extracted at regular intervals (constant temporal distance from each other) we can construct a three-dimensional representation of the sound. Such a representation, which was presented by Moorer and Grey in [4], describes the evolution of the frequency spectrum over time. However, in contrast to Moorer and Grey's representation, which is plotting the amplitude vs. time envelopes of the harmonic sound's individual partials, our representation is plotting amplitude vs. frequency envelopes that are suitable for describing also noise-based sound. We can reduce these dimensions to a single value by integration, essentially computing the volume under the three-dimensional representation of the sound.

After calculating the volume of each sound in this fashion, we can sum the volumes over the collection of sounds to calculate the total volume of the sound space. We can then represent the portion occupied by each sound as the ratio between the individual sound's volume and the space volume. In Figures 6 through 9 we present pie charts of the ratios calculated for the same sounds included in tables 1 through 4 in the orders defined in the previous step. These pie charts are comparable with the clock face commonly used to represent the pitch-class space. However in a pie chart representation of the pitch-class space every slice of the pie would be uniformed size.

Figure 6. Pie representation of sound space 1 (*Balanced* sound objects).

Figure 7. Pie representation of sound space 2 (*Redundant and Homogeneous* sound objects).

Figure 8. Pie representation of sound space 3 (*Accumulation and Sample* sound objects).

Figure 9. Pie representation of sound space 4 (*Excentrics* sound objects).

Following the completion of step 2 each sound is represented by a pair of values. The first value defines the position of the sound within the ordered sound space. The second value is the percentage of the space occupied by this sound. In the next step we use this pair of values to define a probability-based pitch class to sound object mapping.

4.3 Step 3: Mapping Pitch to Sound

The pitch class to sound object mapping relations defined in this step and the correlating probabilities are based on a comparison between the fixed pitch-class space and arbitrary sound spaces. While both type of spaces are ordered, the pitch-class space is equally segmented where as sound spaces' internal segmentation (portion of space occupied by each sound) varies from space to space. The latter's order and segmentation are defined in the first two steps of this method. To conduct this comparison we convert the pie chart presentations of spaces used in the previous step to a stacked bar chart that shows the same information as the pie charts for both the pitch-class space and the sound spaces side by side. The pitch-class-space bar is divided into 12 equal portions. A sound-space bar is divided into a number of portions equal to the number of sounds in the space. Each portion is of the size defined in step 2. Figure 10 shows a bar chart comparing the pitch-class space with an arbitrary sound space.

The mapping relations between pitch classes and sound objects, which are derived from the above comparison, are many-to-many. Therefore we must define two separate mappings for each sound space: pitch classes to sound objects; and sound objects to pitch classes. These mappings produce four possible types of overlaps (see Figure 10):

- a) The pitch class area boundaries are completely enclosed within the sound object area boundaries, e.g., overlap (a) in Figure 10 between pitch class 8 and sound 5.
- b) The sound object area boundaries are completely enclosed within the pitch class area boundaries,

e.g., overlap (b) in Figure 10 between sound 7 and pitch class 10.

- c) The pitch class area overlaps the lower border of the sound object area, e.g., overlap (c) in Figure 10 between pitch class 5 and sound 4.
- d) The pitch class area overlaps the upper border of the sound object area, e.g., overlap (d) in Figure 10 between pitch class 3 and sound 2.

We define a mapping probability between a pitch class and a sound object based on the portion of overlapping area. Larger overlapping area yields higher probability. More specifically, the probability of a pitch class mapping to a sound object is the ratio between the overlapping area and the total area of the pitch class. The probability of a sound object mapping to a pitch class is the ratio between the overlapping area and the total area of the sound object. Hence the method may yield different mapping probabilities when mapping a pitch class to a sound object or when mapping the same sound object to the same pitch class. For example in overlap (a) the mapping of pitch class 8 to sound object 5 is of probability 1.0, however, sound object 5 has lesser probability of mapping to pitch class 8.

Figure 10. A bar chart comparing the internal segmentations of the pitch-class space and an arbitrary sound space, demonstrating the four overlap types.

Figure 11 shows the probability-based mapping relations between the fixed pitch-class space and a sound space including the sound files of the *Balanced* objects TARTYP sub-collection. The mapping is from pitch classes to sound objects and therefore represented by directed arrows. The labels on the arrows represent the mapping probability. In this specific example sound object N (the sound file N.aif), the first in order, occupies the first segment of the sound space which is 19.5% of the space (or 0.195021 as shown in Figure 6) from the bottom edge. Pitch classes 0 and 1 occupy the first two segments of the pitch-class space, which are each 8.33% of the space, i.e., 16.66% of the space measured from the bottom edge. Since the area boundaries of pitch class 0 and pitch class 1 are completely enclosed within the area boundaries of sound object N, the mapping probabilities of pitch class 0

and pitch class 1 to sound object N are both 1.0. Pitch class 2 has mapping relations with three sound objects: its boundaries overlap the upper border of sound object N as well as the lower border of sound object Y'; and sound object X' is completely enclosed within pitch class 2. Since 35% of the area of pitch class 2 overlap with sound object N the mapping probability of pitch class 2 to sound object N is 0.35. In a similar way, based on the percentage of overlapping area the mapping probability of pitch class 2 to sound object X' is 0.6 and the mapping probability of pitch class 2 to sound object Y' is 0.05.

The mapping relations depict in Figure 11 are calculated by a Python module that is incorporated in the lower part of the patch shown in Figure 5. This module receives a list of ratios representing the segmentation of a sound space from the Python module directly above it in the patch and compares this list with a fixed list of ratios representing the segmentation of the pitch class space that is stored in the message above and to the left of it in the patch.

Figure 11. Probability-based mapping relations between the fixed pitch-class space and the sound space of the *Balanced* objects.

5. IMPLEMENTATION

Using the patches shown in Figures 2 through 5, we incorporate our three-step method within a two-fold real-time compositional implementation. In the first part, a sound space of an arbitrary collection of sound objects is introduced and analyzed to define its mapping to the fixed pitch-class space. This part of the implementation is a time-based process constrained by a delay chain to allow real-time playback and analysis of sound files, as required for step 1 and 2 of the method. Once the mapping is defined, it is used in the second part of the implementation along with one of our generative tools, the TARTYP generative grammar tool or the interactive K-Network tool, for real-time composition in both the pitch class and the sound object domains.

Figure 12 shows a component of the patch from Figure 5 that is used in the second part of the implementation,

i.e., the generative real-time composition. This specific component is used when the mapping is in the direction of pitch classes to sound objects and the real-time composition is using the interactive K-Network tool. The latter generates pitch-class sequences as explained in [2]. Every pitch class in these sequences is coupled with a randomly generated number between 0.01 and 1.0. The pair is entered as an argument to the Python module incorporated in the lower part of the patch shown in Figure 5. This module uses the probability-based mapping to select a sound object, i.e., a sound file. More specifically, the module uses the randomly selected number to choose among multiple sound files that may be in mapping relations with the specified pitch class. Considering the mapping shown in Figure 11, when the pitch class is 2, the module would use the random number generator to select among the three possible sound files, weighted accordingly. If the number is between 0.01 and 0.35 sound object N is selected; if it is between 0.36 and 0.95 sound object X' is selected; if it is between 0.96 to 1.0 sound object Y' is selected.

Figure 12. A patch component randomly generating numbers between 0.01 and 1.0 that are coupled with pitch classes for triggering a probability based selection of sounds.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The goal of this study was to create a bridge between Pierre Schaeffer's TARTYP Taxonomy and the transformational Klumpenhouwer Networks as well as to combine our previously developed tools (the TARTYP generative grammar tool and the interactive K-Network tool) in a unified compositional process. We presented a three-step method for creating a probability-based mapping between pitch classes and sound objects, utilizing the mfcc~ object from the timbreID library. We also presented a two-fold implementation that incorporates this method in real-time composition.

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